

Systematic Approach and Ethno Botanical Importance of Plants - Sugali Tribe inhabitants of Adilabad and Komaram Bheem Asifabad Districts, Telangana State, India

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Abstract:

The preliminary investigations of Systematic Approach and Ethno Botanical Importance of Plants used by Sugali Tribe inhabitants of Adilabad and Komaram Bheem Asifabad district, Telangana State, India with their recipes, preparation of drugs, administration, and usage form several centuries. The Sugali tribe possessing rich folklore information forms the prime source and exists scope to extend scientific research in further isolation and characterization of active principle involved in the pharmacological utility. The folklore claims were conducted and collaborated with phyto-chemical evidences of the respective crude drugs. Keeping in view of the fact potential source of medicinal plants of folklore origin need to be

preserved and conserved. 74 crude drugs (*species*) belong to 63 genera and 29 families were collected based on folk-lore knowledge. The pattern of the plant use as per habitat (terrestrial, aquatic/epiphytes), habit (growth form), plant part (tissue) and taxonomic category (Systematically families), nativity and occurrence (wild/cultivated) were established.

Keywords: *Lambadis, Primitive reports, Sugali tribe, Thandas.*

Introduction

The present paper designed with a background of previous studies in Telangana State aimed at to provide an update inventory of Ethno

botanical important of Sugali tribe of northern Telangana state. Lambadas accounted for 64% of Telanganas 3.2 million Scheduled Tribes population. The womenfolk of this tribe particularly present a distinct feature. They are

the most robust among women of Indian origin. They can undergo a great deal of labour with apparent ease. They are mostly living peculiar, ornaments so singularly chosen they are chaste and affable. They use bows, arrows, sword and shields. The common occupation of the lambadies is transport, especially in the hill and forest tracts with difficult access, of grain and other produce on pack bullocks. They live in detached clusters of rude huts, called thandas, at some distance from established villages.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

Adilabad district has an average elevation of 264 m MSL. The district shares its boundaries with Nirmal districts of Telangana to the south,

Komaram Bheem Asifabad on the east. The Kuntala Waterfall, rivers like the Godavari, Painganga, etc flow through the districts. Other waterfalls in Adilabad include pochara waterfall also and Gayatri waterfalls in Adilabad city. Komaram Bheem Asifabad district, officially known as Kumuram Bheem Asifabad district is a district in the Indian state of Telangana. The town of Asifabad is its district headquarters and kagaznagar as its largest town. It is named after Gond tribal leader Komaram Bheem. The district share boundaries with Adilabad, Nirmal, Mancherial districts. Telangana is a semi-arid area and has a predominantly hot and dry climate. The average annual rainfall is about 906 mm, 80% of which received from the South-west monsoon. The areas covered by the Deccan plateau are characterized by hot summers with relatively mild winter.

Figure 1. Map Showing Study Area locations

During study of Systematic Approach and Ethno Botanical Importance of Plants used by Sugali Tribe inhabitants of Sonapur Thanda, Komaram Bheem Asifabad District, Telangana State various (Seasonal wise) field trips (4) were conducted and were vouched (76 X 4) from various natural populations during the period 2020-2023. Collected Ethno Botanical, Cultural Activities Data and Plants specimens collected flowering or fruiting Seasons. Specimens critically observed and identified, herbarium specimens deposited at The University of Trans Disciplinary Health Sciences & Technology (TDU) was done for the taxonomic confirmation. Updated nomenclature, distribution along with field photographs has been presented. All Field data noted carefully field note books, each drug material individually recorded videos and photographs taken with GIS tags.

Primitive Ethno Botanical field collection trips plan to tribal pockets and a number of villages in northern Telangana. Intensive interviews were conducted with tribal Nayakas at their dwellings according to the methods described by Khan (1953), Kapoor & Kapoor (1980), Hemadri (1990), Naqvi (2001), Ramarao (1988), Pullaiha & Kumar (1996), Kumar & Pullaiha (1998), Reddy et al. (1998), Ravishankar & Henry (1992), Ravishankar (1990), Swamy (2009), Omkar et al., (2011), Reddy et al., (2002), Upadhyay & Chauhan (2000), Reddy et al., (2001), Reddy (2002), Reddy & Raju (2002), Raju & Reddy (2005), Raju et al. (2014), Reddy et al. (2007),

Murthy et al. (2011), Suthari et al., (2014), Padmarao & Reddy (1999), Reddy & Raju (2000), Reddy et al. (2010), Sreeramulu et al. (2013). The end database, after previous studies in Sugali tribe various states comprise an update nomenclature for every taxon following the 'Plant List (2013) and APG-IV distribution data, life form data, topography data, complete herbarium data preserved in national and international herbaria representing the study area. Photographs will be provided for all the species. Collection localities will be geo-referenced. The data generated in the present study will be not only useful to taxonomist, ecologists and conservation scientists, but also for a range of research, policy and intellectual property rights.

Results and Discussion

The preliminary investigations of Systematic Approach and Ethno Botanical Importance of Plants used by Sugali Tribe inhabitants of Sonapur Thanda, Komaram Bheem Asifabad District, Telangana State with their recipes, preparation of drugs, administration, and usage form several centuries. 74 crude drugs (*species*) belong to 63 genera and 29 families were collected based on folk-lore knowledge and provided all data. Of the 74 crude drugs wild and naturalized species, 16 are trees, 10 are shrubs, 37 are herbs and remaining 11 are climbers.

Figure 2. Life Form Wise Analysis

Figure 3. Systematic Enumeration

Figure 4. Plant Parts Percentage Wise Used Sugali Tribe

Of the recorded 63 genera 29 families, 11 are represented by one species: Asparagaceae, Burseraceae, Cleomaceae, Combretaceae, Crassulaceae, Juglandaceae, Lythraceae, Sapindaceae, Sapotaceae, Verbenaceae, Vitaceae and The dominant families with respect to number of species are Leguminosae (10), Asteraceae (9), Lamiaceae (8), Apocynaceae (7), Euphorbiaceae (6), Amaranthaceae (4), Cucurbitaceae (3), Phyllanthaceae (3) and Solanaceae (3). Analysis of plants tissues followed tribes used leaves highly 45%, Roots 9%, Whole plants 9%, Small branches 2%, Flowers 6%, Fruits 6%, and remaining seeds 1% (Table 1).

Conclusion

Following species *Abrus precatorius* used in Ayurveda, Siddha, and Unani for snake bite

antidote and aphrodisiac, while in Homeopathy it's used for chronic pain. *Abutilon indicum* used in Ayurveda, Siddha, and Unani for malaria fevers, while in Homeopathy it's used for chronic rheumatism and sciatica. *Acacia nilotica* used in Ayurveda, Siddha, and Unani for furuncles and edema, while in Homeopathy it's used for skin diseases. *Abelmoschus moschatus*, commonly called musk mallow, is native to tropical Asia. It is a compact tender perennial that typically grows in a bushy clump to 1.5-2' tall when grown as an annual. Different parts of the plant have uses in Ayurveda herbal medicine, including as an antispasmodic and to treat gonorrhoea. However, use may result in phytophotodermatitis and it has not been proven safe for use during pregnancy and lactation. *Abrus precatorius* is used in some traditional medicine to treat scratches and sores and wounds caused by dogs, cats and mice, and are also used with other ingredients to treat

leucoderma. The leaves of the herb are used to cure fever, cough and cold. *Acacia nilotica* is widely used. This plant has anti-microbial, anti-plasmodial and antioxidant activity and used for treatment of human immunodeficiency virus, hepatitis C virus and cancer. *Acalypha indica* many therapeutics purposes such as anthelmintic, anti-ulcer, bronchitis, asthma, wound healing, anti-bacterial and other applications. *Acmella paniculata* leaves are used for culinary purposes, and the flowers have been used for their numbing and pain-relieving properties, earning the plant such common names as the toothache plant. In addition, it has been noted to relieve stomatitis, have taste-activating properties, and to induce a salivary response. The leaves or the ashes of the plant, mixed with oil, are applied to cure herpetic eruptions. *Ammannia baccifera* The fresh, bruised leaves have been used in skin diseases as a rubefacient and as an external remedy for ringworm and parasitic skin affection. *Andrographis paniculata* is traditionally used for the treatment of common cold, diarrhoea, fever due to several infective cause, jaundice, as a health tonic for the liver and cardiovascular health, and as an antioxidant. *Butea monosperma* seeds are used for skin ailments; keratitis; piles; urinary discharges; and diseases of the brain, eye, head, and skin. The juice from the plant as well as the oil is antiseptic. *Cleome gynandra* leaves are boiled and marinated in sour milk for 2-3 days and eaten as a nutritious meal, which is believed to improve eyesight, provide energy and cure marasmus. *Clerodendrum phlomidis* used to reduce swelling and inflammation (Shothahara). Warm leaves of Agnimantha are used to relieve severe pain. Agnimantha is useful for low digestive fire (Agnimandya) and improves digestive fire (deepana). Used to expel out extra waste from body (anulomana). *Diplocyclos palmatus* is a slender-stemmed tendril climber commonly called as Shivlingi. Traditionally, this plant has been used in the folk medicine and possesses several activities such as gynaecological, anti-asthmatic, anti-convulsant, anti-venom, anti-inflammatory. *Vitex negundo* decoction of leaves is used for treatment of inflammation, eye-disease, toothache, leucoderma, enlargement of the spleen, ulcers, cancers, catarrhal fever,

rheumatoid arthritis, gonorrhoea, sinuses, scrofulous sores, bronchitis and as tonics. *Xanthium strumarium*, as a traditional herbal medicine, has been extensively applied to treat many diseases, such as rhinitis, nasal sinusitis, headache, gastric ulcer, urticaria, rheumatism bacterial, fungal infections and arthritis. *Boswellia serrata* or Indian frankincense, is a resin herbal extract from the boswellia tree. The tree is used for fodder, timber, medicinal, religious and in cosmetics. *Ixora pavetta*, used to treat malnourishment, lesions, urinary tract disease, skin infection, hepatic disorders. *Salvia plebeia* or sage (*Salvia*) species have been used in traditional medicine for the relief of pain, protecting the body against oxidative stress, free radical damages, angiogenesis, inflammation, bacterial and virus infection, etc. There is little information on the ways in which these values are changing. No studies explore the implications of changing cultural values on forest resource use.

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Table 1. Plants List_Drugs Preparations and Methods Used by Sugali Tribes

S. No	Name of the Species	Family	Vern. Names	Plant parts Use	Preparations/Administration	Medicinal Use
1	<i>Abelmoschus moschatus</i> Medik.	Malvaceae	Rummi Bbenda	Fr	20 gm roots 21 days taken monopaj stage recovering	Menopause and gynecomastia
2	<i>Abrus precatorius</i> L.	Leguminosae	Gurivindba	L, R	Macerated with water/drunk Root Juice/oral 3 times a day seeds powdered/oral	Menorrhoea Snake bite antidote Aphrodisiaca
3	<i>Abutilon indicum</i> (L.) Sweet	Malvaceae	Naahrare Jaad	L	With garlic juice extract/oral	Malarial fevers
4	<i>Acacia nilotica</i> (L.) Delile	Leguminosae	Jaali Jaad	Sb	Heated and placed on the spot for 3 days	Furuncles, Oedema
5	<i>Acalypha ciliata</i> Forssk.	Euphorbiaceae	Adavi pippinta	L	Fresh leaves and bajara 5 gm mixture used orally 2-3 days morning time	Anti-inflammation, anti bacterial, anthelmintic
6	<i>Acalypha indica</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	Pippi	L	Leaves mixed with pepper, garlic extract/oral for 3-6 times.	Used for teeth pain reduce phlegm and in the treatment of cough asthma and other breathing problem
7	<i>Acanthospermum hispidum</i> DC.	Asteraceae	-	L	Leaves direct applied stomach	Abdominal pain
8	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	Dhol Kasiri	L, R, S	Fresh crushed leaves applying mouth and stem daily brushed to teeth	Relief toothache and strong teeth
9	<i>Acmella oleracea</i> (L.) R.K.Jansen	Asteraceae	Akkalkaro	L, F	Leaves are used for pain-relieving properties, Flowers have been used toothache, taste activating properties	Pain-relieving, taste activating properties
10	<i>Acmella paniculata</i> (Wall. ex Dc.) R.K. Jansen	Asteraceae	Vana mogga	Fl	Flowers applied on the tongue below 5-10 year children and used in toothache and infections of throat and gum	Throat and gum infection
11	<i>Acmella radicans</i> (Jacq.) R.K.Jansen	Asteraceae		Fl	Toothache plant is used to treat stomatitis or inflammation of the mouth;	Toothache
12	<i>Aerva lanata</i> (L.) Juss.	Amaranthaceae	Kalobbaaji	L	Fresh leaves (250 gms) collect and boiled leaves direct orally taken 2-3 days cure body pains.	Body Pains
13	<i>Agave americana</i> L.	Asparagaceae	-	L	Dried pulp/roal for week days	Abortifacient
14	<i>Albizia lebbek</i> (L.) Benth.	Leguminosae	-	Sb	Juice (50 ml)/ oral for 3 times	Snake and scorpion bite antidote
15	<i>Ammannia baccifera</i> L.	Lythraceae	-	L	Pulp applied on the area for 3 days Juice with dry chillies/oral for 3 days	Oedema and skin disease Ascariasis and Stomach pain.
16	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> (Burm.f.) Nees	Acanthaceae	-	L	Leaves 5 gm add pepper oral use	Anti inflammatory, antiviral, antioxidant properties
17	<i>Argemone mexicana</i> L.	Papaveraceae	Dathurare Jaad	L	Dry roots, piper and beetle nuts 11 days taken cure weakness	Weakness & gynecomastia
18	<i>Bauhinia racemosa</i> Lam.	Leguminosae		B	Bark is traditionally used as tonic, refrigerant and treatment of ulcers; it is also used skin diseases.	Ulcers, Skin diseases

19	<i>Boswellia serrata</i> Roxb. ex Colebr.	Burseraceae		Bark	Fresh Sap effective anti-inflammatory, it can be an effective painkiller and may prevent the loss of cartilage.	Chronic inflammatory illness, Folk medicine
20	<i>Bridelia montana</i> (Roxb.) Willd.	Phyllanthaceae		L, S, B	Leaf, Stem, bark and root paste applied to the skin for wounds, to the scalp for headache and sore eyes.	Swelling, lesser pain, and lower fevers
21	<i>Bryophyllum pinnatum</i> (Lam.) Oken	Crassulaceae	<i>Ranapala</i>	L	Leaves used for the treatment of wounds, ulcers, piles and to control bleeding	Wounds and ulcers and piles
22	<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.) Taub.	Leguminosae	<i>Dhakadar jaad</i>	L, Fl	5 leaves & Cow milk mixture daily morning 5 days taken ovaries excess of heat controlling	Gynic disorders
23	<i>Calotropis gigantea</i> (L.) Dryand.	Apocynaceae	<i>Aaker Jaad</i>	L	Juice/oral for vomiting.	Antitoxicosis
24	<i>Cardiospermum halicacabum</i> L.	Sapindaceae	-	L	Paste applied on the part	Oedema
25	<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.	Leguminosae	<i>Ramdhanda Jaad</i>	Fl, Fr	Fresh fruits pulp boiled and adds 50 gm jaggery mixture daily 20-30 days taken cure Gastric problems and head nerves cured.	Rheumatism ulcers, skin eruptions
26	<i>Catharanthus pusillus</i> (Murray) G. Don	Apocynaceae	<i>Sadababar</i>	L	Daily morning each leaves directly eaten	Cancer
27	<i>Catharanthus roseus</i> (L.) G. Don	Apocynaceae	<i>Billa Ganneru</i>	L, R	Leaves juice is used in blood dysentery, root paste is used in septic wounds and decoction is used in fever	Diabetes, fever, dysentery
28	<i>Celosia argentea</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	<i>Laambdi bbaaji</i>	R	Extract oral for 3 days	Typhoid fevers
29	<i>Cissus quadrangularis</i> L.	Vitaceae	<i>Nalleru</i>	Wp	Young shoots used for vegetable-helping prevent metabolic syndrome	Bone loss, allergies and asthma
30	<i>Citrullus colosynthis</i> (L.) Schrad.	Cucurbitaceae	-	F	Pulp macerated with garlic, extract/oral for week days fruit pulp squeezed/oral	Psychosis and anxiety Constipation
31	<i>Cleome gynandra</i> L.	Cleomaceae	<i>Bhangroo</i>	R, L	Fresh 2-3 Leaves taken crushed after 2-3 drops taken nose and roots upper epidermis chewable	One side headache and Thyroid problems
32	<i>Clerodendrum phlomidis</i> L.f.	Lamiaceae	-	L	Boiled in water and vapors/inhaled Extract with pepper/oral, 3 times. Leaf extract/oral	Severe and prolonged body ache Constipation and dropsy Debility
33	<i>Cullen corylifolium</i> (L.) Medik.	Leguminosae	<i>Bavanchi</i>	Sd, L	Seeds edible, Leaves used in the treatment of fever, lower back pain, skin ailments	Seeds
34	<i>Dalbergia latifolia</i> Roxb.	Leguminosae	-	L	Leaves shade dry and making powder daily morning mixing 5 grms powder & water taken 4-5 days	Menstruation bleeding controlled

35	<i>Datura metel</i> L.	Solanaceae	<i>Kaalodatura</i>	L	Single leave taken adaxially apply castor oil and heat leaves direct apply or are used as a local application for rheumatic swelling of the joints and Hydrocele	Rheumatic, Swelling Pains and Hydrocele Swelling
36	<i>Diplocyclos palmatus</i> (L.) C. Jeffrey	Cucurbitaceae	<i>Sivaling Jaad</i>	Sd	When drying seeds & Putranjeevika mixture taken 21 days to 60 days	Gynic problems
37	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Dhoodhere Jaad</i>	L	Leaves add garlic & pepper take daily morning	Worm infestation in children
38	<i>Euphorbia prostrata</i> Aiton	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Dhooder jaad</i>	Wp	Plants used for the treatment of piles and effective for treatment of bleeding hemorrhoids	Piles, Bleeding hemorrhoids
39	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> (L.) R. Br. ex Schult.	Apocynaceae	<i>Tagalar zhad</i>	R	Roots powder used leprosy, skin diseases, fever and urinary diseases	Leprosy, fever, asthma and Urinary diseases
40	<i>Hygrophila auriculata</i> (Schumach.) Heine	Acanthaceae		L	The plant used traditional medicine to cure jaundice	Kidney infections, Jaundice
41	<i>Ipomoea obscura</i> (L.) Ker Gawl.	Convolvulaceae	-	Wp	Heated, placed on the spot and dressed juice 20 ml/orl	Wounds, burns, boils skin abscess giddiness and nausea
42	<i>Ixora pavetta</i> Andr.	Rubiaceae	<i>Lokandi</i>	B	Small branch bark boiled 1/3 juice orally after apply 7-15 days strength and Cavity's.	Strength and Cavity's
43	<i>Jasminum azoricum</i> L.	Oleaceae	-	L	Juice applied on the spot Ker-Gahll	Furuncles, Oedema for 3 days
44	<i>Jatropha curcas</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Motarend Jaad</i>	L	Juice 1-2 drops orally	Bacterial and fungal infections
45	<i>Juglans cinerea</i> L.	Juglandaceae		L, Fr	Butternut used by various tonic remedy to treat arthritic joints, headaches, constipation and wounds	Arthritic joints, headaches, constipation and wounds
46	<i>Lantana camara</i> L.	Verbenaceae	<i>Bhootgaanja</i>	L, R	Leaves are used for treating malaria, chickenpox, skin itches and wounds. Roots used for cough.	Wounds, Chickenpox, Skin Allergies and Cough
47	<i>Leucas aspera</i> (Willd.) Link	Lamiaceae	-	L	Extract with pepper, garlic/Oral Extract dropped in the opposite ear of the Pain side	Malaria, intermittent fevers encephalitis migraine
48	<i>Leucas martinicensis</i> (Jacq.) R.Br.	Lamiaceae	<i>Butta Jaad</i>	Wp	Whole plant extract 50 gm and Castor oil 200 ml mixture applying total body 10-15 days cure paralysis disease	Paralysis'
49	<i>Leucas nepetifolia</i> Benth.	Lamiaceae	<i>Aggyabutta</i>	Wp	As it is believed traditionally that the plant having some super natural powers- peoples used the plant dried material in their homes to prevent evil forces	Super natural powers
50	<i>Luffa tuberosa</i> Roxb.	Cucurbitaceae	<i>Kolaar Jaad</i>	R	Juice extracted with 5 gm musambaram/oral 3 times a day for 3 days	Abortifacient

51	<i>Madhuca longifolia</i> (J.Koenig ex L.) J.F.Macbr.	Sapotaceae	<i>Modi Jaad</i>	Fl, Bark	Bark extract is used for dental related problems, rheumatism, and diabetes. Edible flowers & fruits bark used preparation for alcohol.	Rheumatism, Diabetes and Dental problems
52	<i>Martynia annua</i> L.	Martyniaceae	<i>Vaagnathi, Motkathiri</i>	L	Traditionally used in the treatment of epilepsy, sore throat and inflammatory disorders. Leaf paste is used topically on tuberculosis of the lymphatic glands and wounds	Tuberculosis and Lymphatic glands and wounds
53	<i>Merremia emarginata</i> (Burm. f.) Hallier f.	Convolvulaceae	<i>Vunderkhan</i>	L	Leaves are useful as a diuretic and an alternative and used cough, headache and rheumatism	Diuretic, cough, headache and rheumatism
54	<i>Morinda pubescens</i> Sm.	Rubiaceae	<i>Aalare Jaad</i>	Fr	Fruits and Juice have been used in the treatment of Diabetes, high blood pressure and enhance immunity	Diabetes, High BP and Immunity Booster
55	<i>Ocimum basilicum</i> L.	Lamiaceae	<i>Ram thulasi</i>	L	Basil has been used as a traditional medicinal plant for the treatment of headache, cough and worms	Headache, cough and worms
56	<i>Ocimum tenuiflorum</i> L.	Lamiaceae	<i>Thulasi Jaad</i>	L	Leaves orally used	Relieves Cough, fever and oral health
57	<i>Pentanema indicum</i> (L.) Ling	Asteraceae	<i>Motoghavadi</i>	R	Roots were used to kidney problems; Leaves were used to stomach problems	Kidney problems
58	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i> Schumacher & Thonn.	Phyllanthaceae	<i>Koyvala amla</i>	WP	Fresh leaves extract and Curd mix before breakfast 2-5 days.	Jaundice
59	<i>Phyllanthus maderaspatensis</i> L.	Phyllanthaceae	<i>Bhuyaavala</i>	L	Leaves extract 5 gm daily mng orally 5 days taken cure diabetes	Diabetes
60	<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Arend Jaad</i>	L	Fresh leaves taken applied Same oil heated leaves applied anal fistula	Piles
61	<i>Salvia plebeia</i> R.Br.	Lamiaceae		L	Traditionally Leaves are used to treat cough, asthma and toothache	Cough, asthma and toothache
62	<i>Senna occidentalis</i> (L.) Link	Leguminosae	<i>Moto Pombadia Jaad</i>	Fr	5 grams roots powder and cow milk taken 5 days stopping blood vomiting	Hematemesis
63	<i>Solanum americanum</i> Mill.	Solanaceae	<i>Kaasaku</i>	Wp	Decoction of stalk, leaves, roots are good for stomach irritation, pain, nervousness. Fruits has been used for treatment of diabetes.	Pain relief, Irritation and diabetes
64	<i>Solanum melongena</i> L.	Solanaceae	<i>Venganer Jaad</i>	L	Leaves 5 gm and human urine 5 ml both mixture externally use 2-3 drops, recovery ear pains	Ear pain relief
65	<i>Sphaeranthus indicus</i> L.	Asteraceae	<i>Gorakb mundi</i>	Wp	Plant used for the treatment of Gastric	Gastric disorders and Skin diseases

					disorders and Skin diseases	
66	<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.) Skeels	Myrtaceae	Jambu Jaad	B, Sd	Preparation of 5 gm Bark powder, 5 gm Seeds Powder 150 ml water prepare decoction and orally daily mng taken recovered Kidney Diseases and Diabetes controlled. (10-15 days)	Kidney Diseases and Diabetics
67	<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.	Combretaceae	Sadbuda Jaad	Fr	Fruits powder used to protect the liver and treat respiratory conditions, including respiratory tract infections, cough, and sore throat	Bronchitis, Cough and sore throat
68	<i>Thevetia peruviana</i> (Pers.) K. Schum	Apocynaceae	Peelo Ganneri	B	Bark decoction is used to cleanse wounds, to clear out slough and to heal faster	Dysentery, diabetes and yellow urine
69	<i>Tinospora sinensis</i> (Lour.) Merr.	Menispermaceae	Gholvel Jaad	S	Fresh leaves and add Jaggery, Neem Leaves 21, Thulasi single leaves taken mixture after boiling 2 glass of water 5 days using	Typhoid, malaria, diabetes
70	<i>Tridax procumbens</i> (L.) L.	Asteraceae	Phoolallam Jaad	L	30-50 leaves liquid morning 5 days taken kidney stones burning	Kidney stones
71	<i>Tridax procumbens</i> (L.) L.	Asteraceae	Phoolallam Jaad	Wp	Leaf juice use on fresh wounds, aqueous extract	Wounds
72	<i>Vitex negundo</i> L.	Lamiaceae	Kaalo Sameli	L	Leaves green liquid extracted one teaspoon taken and dry roots powdered and goat milk taken 21 days recovered all health's	Gastric and fevers
73	<i>Wrightia arborea</i> (Dennst.) Mabb.	Apocynaceae	Dhabi Phala	L, B	Bark of the stem and roots is regarded as an antidote against snake bites and scorpion stings	Menstrual and renal complaints, snake-bites, tooth-ache and Diarrhea
74	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i> L.	Asteraceae	Motkathiri Jaad	L	Fresh leaves and Stone salt mixture applying teeth	Toothache

Note: B-Bark; S-Seeds; L-Leaves; Small Branch-Sb; F-Flowers; Fr-Fruits; Wp-Whole Plants; R-Roots

Figure 5. A & B. Bullock Cart_ different types used by Sugali Tribes, C. Oxes, D, E, F. Pistil & Mortar_ different types G. Investigator observed *Boswellia serrata* bark collection, H. Native Traditional healer Explained medicinal important of plants, F. Curative Testimonials from the beneficiaries

Figure 6. Showing GIS (Geographic Information System) images, A. *Abelmoschus moschatus* Medik., B. *Acanthospermum hispidum* DC., C. *Achyranthes aspera* L., D. *Aerva lanata* (L.) Juss., E. *Argemone mexicana* L., F. *Diplocyclos palmatus* (L.) C.Jeffrey, G. *Vitex negundo* L., H. *Senna occidentalis* (L.) Link

Figure 7. A. *Abrus precatorius* L., B. *Abutilon indicum* (L.) Sweet, C. *Ammannia baccifera* L., D. *Andrographis paniculata* (Burm.f.) Nees, E. *Boswellia serrata* Roxb. ex Colebr., F. *Bridelia montana* (Roxb.) Willd.

Figure 8. A. *Butea monosperma* (Lam.) Taub., B. *Calotropis gigantea* (L.) Dryand., C. *Cardiospermum halicacabum* L., D. *Catharanthus pusillus* (Murray) G.Don, E. *Catharanthus roseus* (L.) G.Don, F. *Citrullus colosynthis* (L.) Schrad.

Figure 9. A. *Datura metel* L., B. *Hemidesmus indicus* (L.) R. Br. ex Schult., C. *Hygrophila auriculata* (Schumach.) Heine, D. *Jatropha curcas* L., E. *Leucas aspera* (Willd.) Link, F. *Leucas martinicensis* (Jacq.) R.Br., G. *Madhuca longifolia* (J.Koenig ex L.) J.F.Macbr., H. *Martynia annua* L.

Figure 10. A. *Morinda pubescens* Sm., B. *Ocimum basilicum* L., C. *Ocimum tenuiflorum* L., D. *Phyllanthus amarus* Schumach. & Thonn., E. *Sphaeranthus indicus* L., F. *Terminalia bellirica* (Gaertn.) Roxb., G. *Xanthium strumarium* L.